

Corrosion resistance hybrid sol gel coating: its synthesis and characterizations

Nitin Kamble¹, Yolanda Castro² Alicia Durán² and Dušan Galusek¹

¹ FunGlass, Alexander Dubček University of Trenčín
(E-mail: nitin.kamble@tnuni.sk)

² Instituto de Cerámica y Vidrio, CSIC

ABSTRACT

Hybrid organic/inorganic structures show excellent mechanical, thermal and optical properties, combining the stability of ceramic materials with the flexibility of polymeric ones. During the last few years, effort has been devoted to the synthesis of hybrid polymers obtained by reaction with organic and inorganic compounds due to the remarkable properties of these materials [1-3]. Protective organic coatings are widely employed as primers to protect steel surfaces from corrosion. However, poor adhesion of the coating material to the steel can cause not only delamination of the coating material, but the corrosion of the steel substrate beneath the coating material. On the other hand, protective inorganic coatings can provide excellent properties in thermal shock resistance, creep resistance, high temperature strength and thermal stability. Metal oxidation is one of the main problems found in industry and interest in the production of protective coatings has increased. Several materials have been applied to solve this problem, including organic and inorganic polymers.

Hybrid polymers are a very interesting and promising area of study. Alkoxy group-functionalized amorphous silica-based inorganic-organic hybrid materials were designed and synthesized from PHPS by chemical modification. The sol-gel matrix was produced from, tetraethoxysilane (TEOS), hybrid precursor organically functionalized PHPS. The evolution of the solutions, mainly the chemical structure, during the processes of hydrolytic condensation and organic polymerization was studied as a function of the sol concentration through Fourier transformed infrared spectroscopy (FTIR). Single layer will be deposited on glass substrate by chemical dip coating method.

Polysilazane bands at $\sim 3385\text{ cm}^{-1}$ (N–H stretching mode), $\sim 2950\text{ cm}^{-1}$ (C–H symmetric stretching mode), $\sim 2125\text{ cm}^{-1}$ (Si–H symmetric stretching mode), $\sim 1250\text{ cm}^{-1}$ (C–H symmetric deformation mode) and $\sim 1150\text{ cm}^{-1}$ (N–H bending mode) [4,5]. After the selective crosslinking reactions, the bands concerning N–H and Si–H groups became smaller, indicating the consumption of these functional groups. The decrease of a broad peak at $\sim 3400\text{ cm}^{-1}$ corresponding to OH groups also confirms that formation of Si–O–Si bond [6] which is indicated in fig.1 a) and 1b). In Fig.2 a) and b) shows area under curve and area decreases as reaction time increases. Firstly, the Si–H groups react rapidly with water, forming Si–OH groups and generating hydrogen molecules. In the next step, the silanol intermediates may react with each other by condensation to siloxane units and the formed water molecules attack the Si–N bonds, which again generates silanol groups. This reaction creates a dense hybrid silica network.

Fig.1: a) FTIR spectra of Si-H peak b) FTIR spectra of Si-NH peak.

Fig.2: a) Area under curve of Si-H peak b) Area under curve of Si-NH peak

Conclusion: Crack-free and optically transparent hybrid organic–inorganic coatings were deposited onto glass from sol prepared by acid-catalyzed hydrolytic polycondensation of TEOS, MPS and Durazane mixtures, at various TEOS/MPS/Durazane molar ratios, followed by radical polymerization of Aibn. FTIR results showed that the degree of polycondensation increases as the synthesis time increases and the formation of very strong Si–O–Si bonds, while the extent of organic polymerization is essentially unaffected by the amount of acid and ethanol concentration. Maximum coating thickness till now obtained upto 1 μ m through this hybrid sol.

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